

Enhancing Land Carbon–Nitrogen Mass Conservation in CMIP Earth System Model Data Reporting

— A Summary of Communications Between ESM Teams, C4MIP Leads, and the CMIP7 Data Request

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Background

Carbon and nitrogen cycle data from Earth system models (ESMs) support numerous downstream analyses. From the CMIP6 published data, we identified a mass conservation issue in the carbon–nitrogen cycle data: the flux data and pool size data often do not match (i.e., $influx - outflux \neq change\ in\ pool\ size$; Tang et al., 2025). This discrepancy is common across many models and experiments, with mismatches reaching several hundred gigatons of carbon in some cases. Together with co-authors, we investigated potential causes and provided recommendations to the relevant communities in our publication (Tang et al., 2025).

To further address this issue, I coordinated communications between ESM teams worldwide and C4MIP leads to clarify two key points:

1. **How ESM teams interpret the CMIP-requested variables**
2. **What C4MIP and the CMIP Data Request expect ESMs to report**

This document summarizes these communications and aims to minimize misunderstandings between ESM teams and CMIP/C4MIP regarding data requirements.

Declaration

The information presented here is based on communications between ESM teams, C4MIP leads, and the CMIP7 Data Request team. This is a community-driven effort to provide guidance and clarification on CMIP variables relevant to the carbon and nitrogen cycles, with a focus on ensuring mass conservation (i.e., pool size data should be consistent with reported fluxes).

Given the time required to modify variable definitions or add/remove variables from CMIP/C4MIP, this document serves as a **living reference** (with an [online version](#) available for timely commenting and direct discussion) intended to prevent similar issues in CMIP7 by clarifying key variable definitions. **It is highly suggested to be reviewed and considered by ESM teams before submitting CMIP7 data.**

We emphasize that our analysis does **NOT** imply mass conservation issues within the models themselves. The problem lies primarily in **data reporting**. Addressing this is critical for resolving the issue.

I, Gang Tang, emphasize that the following represents **comments and suggestions** intended to help address the **data issue**. They are based primarily on my background in global carbon–nitrogen cycles and Earth system science, my understanding of data reporting, and my involvement in the CMIP7 Data Request, supplemented by feedback from ESM teams and input from C4MIP leads. This is **NOT** an official change to the CMIP Data Request or CMIP variable definitions; such decisions require further discussion within the MIPs and fall outside my role as a volunteer coordinator and an individual researcher concerned with data quality.

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With support from C4MIP leads (Chris Jones and Vivek Arora) and contributions from multiple ESM teams

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Top-Level Carbon-Nitrogen Mass Conservation Check for ESMs

Figure 1. The C4MIP requested carbon-nitrogen cycle variables (adapted from Jones et al., 2016)

Mass conservation requires that flux data match the pool size data; that is:
influx – outflux = change in pool size.

To ensure this, we recommend verifying the following five equations at the **global annual-mean level**, allowing for small numerical tolerances (e.g., cumulative mismatch < 5 GtC for total carbon).

Note: For carbon flux, the CMIP variables do not include fCLeach or fLandToOcean. Instead, fCLandToOcean is the sole variable used to represent the carbon flux from land to ocean.

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Equation 1:

- $c_{Land} = c_{Veg} + c_{Litter} + c_{Soil} + c_{Product}$

C4MIP intention:

- Total land carbon should equal the sum of its sub-pools.

Facts:

- This equation is not satisfied in some cases in CMIP6 ESM data.

Comments:

- This is surprising because these are state variables, which should be easier to reconcile. Potential causes cannot be inferred from data alone.

Suggestions:

- Despite its simplicity, ESM teams are encouraged to perform this check.

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Equation 2:

- $dcLand / dt = npp - rh - fAnthDisturb - fFireNat - fProductDecomp - fCLandToOcean$

OR

- $dcLand / dt = npp - rh - fDeforestToAtmos - fHarvestToAtmos - fFireNat - fProductDecomp - fCLandToOcean$

C4MIP intention:

- All emissions from anthropogenic activities on land (excluding fossil fuel emissions) that are directly released to the atmosphere should be included in fAnthDisturb (either via fDeforestToAtmos or fHarvestToAtmos).
- fAnthDisturb should equal the sum of fDeforestToAtmos and fHarvestToAtmos.
- Natural fire emissions should be reported as fFireNat.

Facts:

- From CMIP6 data, very few models reported fFireNat.
- From CMIP6 data, most models reported fDeforestToAtmos and fHarvestToAtmos, but not fAnthDisturb.

Feedback from ESM teams:

- Most ESMs cannot separate natural and anthropogenic fire, explaining the lack of fFireNat.
- Many report total fire emissions as fFire, which is a CMIP requested variable but not in the C4MIP.

Comments:

- Definitions of npp, rh, fProductDecomp, and fCLandToOcean are clear.
- Definitions of fAnthDisturb, fDeforestToAtmos, and fHarvestToAtmos are not very clear.
- Strict adherence to current definitions can lead to double counting between fAnthDisturb (or its components) and fFire.
- Definitions of fDeforestToAtmos and fHarvestToAtmos do not clearly specify treatment of fire-related emissions.

Suggestions:

First, use the following updated/clarified variable definitions:

- fDeforestToAtmos: Carbon mass flux from all the **land cover change**, excluding those caused by fire, that goes straight into atmosphere, for example, emission from deforestation.
- fHarvestToAtmos: Carbon mass flux from all the **land management**, excluding those caused by fire, that goes straight into atmosphere, for example, emission from harvest and grazing.
- fFire: Carbon mass flux from **all the anthropogenic and natural fire**.
- fAnthDisturb: the sum of fDeforestToAtmos and fHarvestToAtmos - but note it **does not include any fire**. This variable is kept for models which cannot separate emissions from land cover change and land management. Note fAnthDisturb should **never include any fossil fuel emissions**.

Second, use the following updated mass conservation equations:

- $dcLand / dt = npp - rh - fAnthDisturb - fFire - fProductDecomp - fCLandToOcean$

OR

- $dcLand / dt = npp - rh - fDeforestToAtmos - fHarvestToAtmos - fFire - fProductDecomp - fCLandToOcean$

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Equation 3:

- $nOrganic = nVeg + nLitter + nSoil + nProduct$

C4MIP intention:

- Total organic nitrogen should equal the sum of its sub-pools.

Facts:

- This equation is not satisfied in many cases in CMIP6 ESM data.

Comments:

- This is surprising because these are state variables, which should be easier to reconcile. Potential causes cannot be inferred from data alone.

Suggestions:

- Despite its simplicity, ESMs with a nitrogen cycle are encouraged to perform this check.

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Equation 4:

- $dnOrganic / dt = fBNF + fNup - fNnetmin - fNAnthDisturb$

Facts:

- Many ESMs, though with a nitrogen cycle, do not provide $fNnetmin$ and $fNAnthDisturb$ in CMIP6 data.

Comments:

- This equation itself should be unambiguous. We emphasize that $fNAnthDisturb$ is a composite flux representing all anthropogenic nitrogen emissions that leave organic pools and are released directly to the atmosphere—for example, emissions from deforestation, harvest, product decay, fire, and related processes.
- Due to incomplete data reporting, we are unable to verify this equation in the CMIP6 data.

Suggestions:

- ESMs with a nitrogen cycle should provide $fNnetmin$ and $fNAnthDisturb$, if modelled.

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Equation 5:

- $dnMineral / dt = fNdep + fNfert + fNnetmin - fNloss - fNup$

OR

- $dnMineral / dt = fNdep + fNfert + fNnetmin - fNgas - fNleach - fNup$

Facts:

- Most ESMs report $fNgas$ and/or $fNleach$ instead of the Tier-1 variable $fNloss$.
- The $fNfert$ is not reported in many cases in the CMIP6 data.

Comments:

- Both approaches for mass conservation are acceptable. However, we emphasize that regardless of which variables are reported, the corresponding mass conservation equation must be satisfied (i.e., $fNloss = fNgas + fNleach$).
- The lack of $fNfert$ is confusing as we are not sure if it is not modelled or just not reported.

Suggestions:

- ESMs should always report $fNloss$ —regardless of whether $fNgas$ and $fNleach$ are reported—as the total nitrogen loss from the mineral nitrogen pool.
- $fNfert$ should be reported if the model has the representation.

Conclusion

From these communications, we learned that many ESMs implement internal mass conservation checks. However, the presence of mass conservation issues in CMIP6 data suggests that inconsistencies occur between model outputs and data reporting—issues that only model teams can fully identify and resolve.

From a data user's perspective, complete and accurate data are essential to verify mass conservation, which is fundamental for any downstream analysis and interpretation. Achieving this requires effort from both sides:

- Data providers (ESM teams): to report complete data under the correct variables.
- Data request frameworks (CMIP, C4MIP, and other MIPs): to define clear variable specifications and provide precise guidance.

Currently, the CMIP Data Request primarily focuses on scientific questions rather than data quality control. We hope this document represents an initial step toward addressing these issues and contributes to future improvements in C4MIP, the CMIP Data Request, and tools like ESMEvalTool.

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